

The Electronegativity of Hydrogen

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Following an earlier method given by Mande *et al.* for evaluating the electronegativity values spectroscopically, we have in the present work determined the electronegativity of hydrogen by extrapolation of the electronegativity values of the group IA elements, which have the outer electronic configuration ns^1 , and their atomic numbers. Our value of the electronegativity for hydrogen, which is essentially the property of the donor hydrogen atom like that of all elements of the IA group, comes out to be 1.29. This value is considerably smaller than the values given hitherto by Pauling and other workers. The implications of this smaller value are discussed in the light of some experimental results.

X-Ray spectroscopy has contributed immensely to the understanding of the periodic table of the elements and chemical bonding in molecules in which elements come together to form stable chemical systems. Professor Hira Lal Nigam is one of the pioneering workers in modern inorganic chemistry. Amongst the chemists in India he is the first to have taken keen interest in this field and to have realised the importance of X-ray spectroscopy. The present article is dedicated to him in appreciation of his untiring efforts during the last many decades to apply X-ray spectroscopic methods to chemistry.

The concept of electronegativity, first proposed by Pauling¹ is important in chemistry as well as in physics since it helps in understanding how atoms of different elements combine to form molecules. According to Pauling¹, electronegativity is defined as "the power of an atom to attract electrons towards itself in a molecule". Several scales²⁻¹¹ of electronegativity have been proposed so far. The first scale of electronegativity given by Pauling¹ is based on thermochemical data. The scale given by Allred and Rochow⁸ employs the concept of the attractive force of an atom, which is inherent in Pauling's definition. For their calculations Allred and Rochow employed the values of the effective nuclear charge using Slater's method¹² which is quite arbitrary. Mande *et al.*^{13,14} later gave a scale of electronegativity which is based on the attractive force concept but employs the values of the

effective nuclear charge, making use of the Dirac equation for orbital energies¹⁵ in which the experimental X-ray/electron spectroscopic data are employed to obtain the electronic screening parameters. According to Mulley¹⁶ this scale is more reliable and reasonable since it makes use of experimental data to obtain the values of the effective nuclear charges. Very recently Luo and Benson¹⁷ have given a new scale of electronegativity which is based on an extension of Yuan's scale¹⁸ which makes use of unshielded core potential of atoms. They have plotted Pauling's values (χ_P) against V_X , the unshielded core potential of the atom X at its covalent radius. The linear variation between (χ_P) and V_X has enabled these authors¹⁷ to refine Pauling's electronegativity values. The sustained interest in this field can be attributed to the fact that it is practically a direct consequence of fundamental concepts of modern chemistry and can be used to explain many physico-chemical properties of atoms, groups of atoms and molecules.

The evaluation of the electronegativity of hydrogen (χ_H) has always been a difficult problem. According to Sanderson¹⁹ "the evaluation of electronegativity of hydrogen remains, unfortunately, somewhat speculative". Pauling has given the value of electronegativity of hydrogen as 2.1[‡]. Some other workers, viz. Sanderson³, Gordy and Thomas⁴, Inamoto and Masuda⁵, Boyd and Markus⁶, Mulliken⁷, Allred and Rochow⁸, Yuan¹⁸, Wells²⁰,

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‡Unfortunately, some authors have been giving Pauling's value of electronegativity of hydrogen as 2.2.

Zhang²¹ and William²² have given the values of electronegativity for hydrogen as 2.31, 2.18, 2.00, 1.94, 2.28, 2.2, 2.70, 2.28, 2.271 and 0.00 respectively. Luo and Benson¹⁷ argued that the electronegativity value of hydrogen should be reduced substantially to remove what is called 'the hydrogen anomaly'. They have given the value of χ_H as 1.61. In the present paper we are making a fresh attempt to evaluate χ_H the electronegativity of hydrogen, which we feel, may throw some light on the hydrogen anomaly.

Evaluation of the electronegativity of hydrogen :

Mande *et al.*^{13,14} have given a scale of electronegativity which is based on the physical interpretation of the electronegativity of an atom as the attractive electrostatic force it exerts at a distance equal to its covalent radius. To estimate this force, Z_{eff} (effective nuclear charge) values at the periphery of the atoms were calculated using a method earlier employed by Mande and Damle¹⁵ for inner shells. This method essentially consists in feeding spectroscopic data of energies in the Dirac equation and then evaluating the effective nuclear charge ($Z - \sigma$), where σ is the screening parameter. For calculating the electronegativity values, Mande *et al.* have calculated the effective charge values of atoms for their outermost atomic orbitals. They have normalised their resultant force values to Pauling's scale of electronegativity through the relation,

$$\chi = \frac{0.778Z_{\text{eff}}}{r_c^2} + 0.5 \quad (1)$$

where r_c stands for the covalent radius of the concerned element. Using the above equation, they were able to give the electronegativity values of elements between $Z = 3$ to 92. The electronegativity of hydrogen could not be calculated since it is not possible to estimate the effective nuclear charge for hydrogen.

So far as the electronic structure is concerned hydrogen belongs to the group IA of the periodic table, in which all the elements are characterised by a single *s*-electron in their outermost orbital. We shall therefore try to evaluate the value of χ_H by the extrapolation of the electronegativity values of the remaining group IA elements. A curve showing the variation of χ values of these elements with atomic

number (Z) is shown in Fig. 1. This curve can be described by the equation,

$$\chi = A_0 + A_1Z + A_2Z^2 + A_3Z^3 \quad (2)$$

where $A_0 = 1.35249$, $A_1 = -6.25496 \times 10^{-2}$, $A_2 = 1.51706 \times 10^{-3}$ and $A_3 = -1.00983 \times 10^{-5}$. The extrapolation of the curve for $Z = 1$ gives the value of χ_H as 1.29 ± 0.02 . The correlation coefficient of

Fig. 1 Variation of the electronegativity values of the group IA elements with atomic number Z.

the curve is found to be 0.997, which indicates that equation (2) is most probably the best fit for the curve. Our value of the electronegativity of hydrogen is significantly smaller than those given by Pauling and other workers including Luo and Benson. It may be emphasised here that our value of hydrogen is essentially the property of the donor hydrogen atom like that of the remaining elements of the IA group. We shall try to examine the consequences of our χ_H value by correlation with experimental results in the following sections. However, before doing so, we shall point out another interesting feature which is borne out by Fig. 1.

It was not possible for Mande *et al.*¹⁴ to give in the earlier work the value of the electronegativity of francium ($Z = 87$) because the term value for the valence shell for this element is not available from XPS work. By extrapolating the curve in Fig. 1, on the high Z side we obtain the value of χ_{Fr} as 0.74.

TABLE 1—DATA ON IONICITIES AND HEATS OF FORMATION FOR CRYSTALLINE (c) AND GASEOUS (g) HALIDES

Sl. no.	Compd.	Heat of formation ΔH_f^0 (kcal mol ⁻¹)	Electronegativity differences	Ionicity I_M
1.	HF*	-64.20 (g)	3.05	0.90
2.	HCl*	-22.06 (g)	1.68	0.51
3.	HBr*	-8.66 (g)	1.60	0.47
4.	HI*	+6.20 (g)	1.27	0.33
5.	LiF*	-146.3 (c)	3.17	0.92
6.	LiCl*	-53.00 (g)	1.80	0.56
7.	LiBr*	-41.00 (g)	1.72	0.52
8.	LiI*	-16.00 (g)	1.39	0.38
9.	NaF	-136.00 (c)	3.48	0.95
10.	NaCl*	-43.50 (g)	2.11	0.67
11.	NaBr	-36.33 (g)	2.03	0.64
12.	NaI	-20.94 (g)	1.70	0.52
13.	KF*	-134.46 (c)	3.72	0.97
14.	KCl*	-51.60 (g)	2.35	0.75
15.	KBr*	-93.73 (c)	2.27	0.72
16.	KI*	-78.31 (c)	1.94	0.61
17.	RbF	-131.28 (c)	3.73	0.97
18.	RbCl	-102.90 (c)	2.36	0.75
19.	RbBr	-93.03 (c)	2.28	0.73
20.	RbI	-78.50 (c)	1.95	0.61
21.	CsF*	-126.9 (c)	3.52	0.95
22.	CsCl*	-103.5 (c)	2.15	0.69
23.	CsBr	-94.3 (c)	2.07	0.66
24.	CsI*	-80.5 (c)	1.74	0.53
25.	IBr*	+9.75 (g)	0.33	0.03
26.	ICl*	+4.20 (g)	0.41	0.04

*Compounds considered by Pauling (Ref. 1).

This value agrees very well with the value 0.7 given by Pauling and is also not quite far off from that (0.86) given by Allred and Rochow, which supports our method of determining χ_H .

Ionicity and heats of formation of binary compounds :

It is well-known that ΔH_f^0 , the heat of formation of a binary compound AB, is related to the electronegativity difference ($\chi_A - \chi_B$). In Table 1 are given the data taken from literature^{2,3} on the heats of formation of some binary compounds in gaseous as well as crystalline states. The ionicities, I_M , calculated using Pauling's formula,

$$I = 1 - \exp\left[-0.25(\chi_A - \chi_B)^2\right] \quad (3)$$

and the values of electronegativity given by Mande *et al.* are also listed in Table 1. We have plotted the ΔH_f^0 values against I_M in Fig. 2. We note that the scatter of the points in Fig. 2 is quite large. We have drawn a similar curve (not shown here) using ionicities obtained from the electronegativity values

of Pauling's scale. The two curves are more or less similar in nature and do not help us to arrive at any judgement of χ_H in either of the scales.

Fig. 2. Variation of heat of formation (ΔH_f^0) of halides with ionicity.

Heats of formation of alkyl derivatives :

One can generally expect that in organic compounds in which there are large number of hydrogen atoms, the effect of χ_H will be more dominant. We have therefore tried to correlate the data on the heats of formation of a number of alkyl derivatives with the electronegativity differences ($\chi_C - \chi_X$), where χ_C is the electronegativity value for the carbon atom and χ_X are those for the atoms N, O, F, S, Cl, Br and I directly bonded to the carbon atom. For this correlation, following the work of Shaw and Benson²⁴, we have considered the differences

$$[\Delta H_f^0(RX) - \Delta H_f^0(R'X)] = \Delta\Delta H_f^0(RX/R'X)$$

where $R \equiv \text{CH}_3$ and $R' \equiv \text{C}_2\text{H}_5$ or $i\text{-C}_3\text{H}_7$ or $t\text{-C}_4\text{H}_9$. In Table 2 are given the data on heats of formation

of alkyl derivatives taken from literature²⁵. In Table 3 are given values of $\Delta\Delta H_f^0$ along with those of $\Delta\chi = (\chi_C - \chi_X)$. We have drawn in Fig. 3 plots between $\Delta\Delta H_f^0$ and $\Delta\chi$ which are found to be linear as expected from the theoretical considerations shown by Schleyer *et al.*²⁶⁻²⁸. Similar graphs were obtained by Luo and Benson²⁹, who plotted the $\Delta\Delta H_f^0$ values against the values of V_X which they considered as a measure of electronegativity. From the analysis of their curves Luo and Benson have estimated the $\Delta\Delta H_f^0$ values of $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{F}$, $i\text{-C}_3\text{H}_7\text{F}$ and $t\text{-C}_4\text{H}_9\text{F}$ as -66.3 ± 0.5 , -76.2 ± 0.5 and -86.9 ± 0.5 kcal mol⁻¹ respectively, which are substantially different from the experimental values -62.9 and -69.0 kcal mol⁻¹ for $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{F}$ and $i\text{-C}_3\text{H}_7\text{F}$ respectively, while the experimental value for $t\text{-C}_4\text{H}_9\text{F}$ is not reported. The

TABLE 2—DATA ON HEATS OF FORMATION (ΔH_f^0 ; kcal mol⁻¹) OF ALKYL DERIVATIVES

Sl. no.	X	Alkyl group			
		CH ₃	C ₂ H ₅	i-C ₃ H ₇	t-C ₄ H ₉
1.	F	-56.80	—	—	—
2.	Cl	-19.59	-26.83	-35.00	-43.80
3.	Br	-9.02	-15.30	-23.20	-32.00
4.	I	3.29	-2.00	-10.00	-17.60
5.	H	-17.89	-20.24	-24.82	-32.15
6.	OH	-48.06	-56.03	-65.11	-74.67
7.	SH	-5.49	-11.02	-18.22	-26.17
8.	NH ₂	-5.50	-11.00	-20.00	-28.65
9.	CH ₃	-20.24	-24.82	-32.15	-39.67

TABLE 3—DIFFERENCES $\Delta\Delta H_f^0$ AND $(\chi_C - \chi_X)$

X	$(\chi_C - \chi_X)$	$\Delta\Delta H_f^0$ (EtX/MeX)	$\Delta\Delta H_f^0$ (i-PrX/MeX)	$\Delta\Delta H_f^0$ (t-BuX/MeX)
F	-1.61	—	—	—
Cl	-0.24	-7.24	-15.41	-24.21
Br	-0.16	-6.28	-14.18	-22.98
I	0.17	-5.29	-13.29	-20.89
H	1.44	-2.35	-6.93	-14.26
OH	-0.98	-7.97	-17.05	-26.61
SH	0.10	-5.53	-12.73	-20.68
NH ₂	-0.53	-5.50	-14.50	-23.15
CH ₃	0.00	-4.58	-11.91	-19.43

large differences between the experimental values and the estimated ones have led Luo and Benson to comment that the experimental values may themselves be in error. Our estimated values of ΔH_f^0 from the curve in Fig. 3 for C_2H_5F , $i-C_3H_7F$ and $t-C_4H_9F$ are found to be -65.9 ± 0.5 , -76.4 ± 0.5 and -86.9 ± 0.5 kcal mol⁻¹ respectively, which are in good agreement with those given by Luo and Benson. Our work also brings out the need for the experimental redetermination of the values of ΔH_f^0 .

Fig. 3. Plots between $\Delta\Delta H_f^0$ and $(\chi_c - \chi_x)$.

The present comparison between our results on ΔH_f^0 with those of Luo and Benson does not indicate the superiority of our values of electronegativity, unequivocally. Hence to test the potentiality of our χ values we shall consider the case of CCl_4 . Thomas³⁰ made an evaluation of charge on the carbon atom in CCl_4 using Gordy's approach of ionicity [$q_G^P = \sum 0.5 [\chi_A - \chi_B]$] employing the electronegativity values of Pauling. He estimated the charge on carbon atom q_G^P to be $+1.0e$. If we use the electronegativity values of Luo and Benson, we get q_G^{LB} to be $+3.7e$. Both these values do not at all agree with the value ($+0.48e$) determined by Gordy³¹ from nuclear quadrupole coupling data. In

our scale $\chi_C = 2.73$ and $\chi_{Cl} = 2.97$, which give the charge on the carbon atom in CCl_4 as $+0.48e$, in complete agreement with Gordy's work.

Nmr ¹³C shifts and group electronegativity :

Bergmann and Hinze³² calculated the group electronegativity values of a number of organic molecules using the basic concept of Mulliken about atomic electronegativity and charge distribution between atoms, using a rigorous quantum mechanical approach. They plotted the group electronegativity values obtained by them versus the difference δ_{NMR} of ¹³C-chemical shifts in the nmr spectra of the CH_2 - and CH_3 -carbon atoms in several ethyl compounds. We note that the scatter of the points in their curve is quite large.

In order to test the correlation of our value of χ_H with δ_{NMR} we have considered only the simplest molecules of the families CH_3X , CH_2X_2 , CH_2XY and CHX_3 , where X and Y are halogen atoms. The group electronegativity values of these molecules were calculated using Sanderson's method¹⁹ which consists of taking the geometric mean of the electronegativity values of the individual atoms in the molecule. In Table 4 are given our calculated group electronegativity values (χ_{gr}^M) using the scale of

TABLE 4—DATA ON ¹³C NMR CHEMICAL SHIFTS AND GROUP ELECTRONEGATIVITIES IN HALOMETHANES

Sl no.	Compd.	Chemical Shift δ_{NMR}	Group electronegativity χ_{gr}^M
1.	CH ₃ F	4.26	1.91
2.	CH ₃ Cl	3.05	1.77
3.	CH ₂ Cl ₂	5.33	2.09
4.	CHCl ₃	7.25	2.47
5.	CH ₃ Br	2.68	1.76
6.	CH ₂ Br ₂	4.94	2.07
7.	CHBr ₃	6.82	2.43
8.	CH ₃ I	2.16	1.72
9.	CH ₂ I ₂	3.90	1.97
10.	CHI ₃	4.93	2.26
11.	CHClBr ₂	7.20	2.45
12.	CH ₂ ClBr	5.16	2.08
13.	CH ₂ ClI	4.99	2.03

Mande *et al.* and the value χ_H as obtained in the present work. This table also includes the ¹³C nmr shifts data for the halomethanes taken from

literature³³. In Fig. 4 are plotted the group electronegativity values (χ_{gr}^M) against ^{13}C nmr shifts.

Fig. 4. Plots of ^{13}C nmr chemical shifts versus group electronegativity, χ_{gr}^M .

We obtain three distinct curves for CH_3X , CH_2X_2 and CH_2XY and CHX_3 molecules. These three different curves bring out, as is well-known, that the nmr shift is essentially the property of a group. Within a group δ_{NMR} is found to increase with the ionicity of a molecule as is evident from the

electronegativity values of the halogen atoms. A similar attempt was made by us using the group electronegativity values obtained from Pauling's scale. The plot drawn between δ_{NMR} and χ_{gr}^p (not shown here) indicates that all the values of δ_{NMR} lie on almost a single linear curve which cannot be resolved into three separate lines. This fact may be attributed to the higher value of χ_{H} assigned to hydrogen by Pauling.

X-Ray photoelectron spectra and electro-negativity:

Several workers³⁴⁻⁴¹ have determined the XPS core level shifts of carbon *1s*-electron in a wide variety of organic compounds. Following Siegbahn's pioneering work³⁸, it has been customary to correlate the observed XPS data with charges calculated from the electronegativity values. In Table 5 we have given the values of the carbon *1s*-level binding energies in halomethanes taken from literature^{38,42,43} and for the iodo-methanes the binding energy values were estimated from the graph (Fig. 7.27 (a) p. 284) given in Ref. 44. The table also includes values of charge q which is taken as $\Sigma(\chi_{\text{I}} - \chi_{\text{H}})$, where $(\chi_{\text{I}} - \chi_{\text{H}})$ is the difference between the electronegativity values

TABLE 5- DATA ON CARBON *1s* BINDING ENERGIES IN HALOMETHANES AND SUM OF ELECTRONEGATIVITY DIFFERENCES

Sl no.	Compd.	C <i>1s</i> B. E. (eV)	Chemical shift w.r.t. CH_4 (eV)	$\sum_{\text{I}} (\chi_{\text{I}} - \chi_{\text{H}})$	$\sum_{\text{I}} (\chi_{\text{C}} - \chi_{\text{I}})$
1.	CH_4	290.70	0.00	0.00	5.76
2.	CH_3F	293.50	2.80	3.05	2.70
3.	CH_2F_2	296.30	5.60	6.10	-0.34
4.	CHF_3	299.00	8.30	9.15	-3.39
5.	CF_4	301.70	11.00	12.20	-6.44
6.	CH_3Cl	292.30	1.60	1.68	4.08
7.	CH_2Cl_2	293.80	3.10	3.36	2.40
8.	CHCl_3	295.00	4.30	5.04	0.72
9.	CCl_4	296.20	5.50	6.72	-0.96
10.	CH_3Br	291.70	1.00	1.60	4.16
11.	CH_2Br_2	293.00	2.30	3.20	2.56
12.	CHBr_3	293.80	3.10	4.80	0.96
13.	CBr_4	294.70	4.00	6.40	-0.64
14.	CH_3I	291.05	0.35	1.27	4.49
15.	CH_2I_2	291.62	0.92	2.54	3.22
16.	CHI_3	292.24	1.54	3.81	1.95
17.	CI_4	(292.70)*	2.00	5.08	0.68

*Value estimated from our work. Experimental B.E. is not available.

of the ligand i and hydrogen, and the summation is carried over all the ligands attached to the carbon atom (or, effectively over the halogens since $\chi_{\text{H}} - \chi_{\text{H}} = 0$). In Fig. 5(a) we have plotted following Thomas³⁰ the values of these carbon $1s$ core level shifts against the values of q . The curve in this figure is obtained using the values of Pauling's

Fig. 5(a). Plot between carbon $1s$ -binding energy shifts (relative to methane) for halomethanes¹ and $\sum_1 (\chi_i - \chi_{\text{H}})$ as per Pauling's scale : (O) fluoromethanes, (Δ) chloromethanes, (\square) bromomethanes and (\oplus) iodomethanes.

Fig. 5(b). Plot between carbon $1s$ -binding energy shifts (relative to methane) for halomethanes and $\sum_1 (\chi_i - \chi_{\text{H}})$ as per Mande and coworkers' scale : (O) fluoromethanes, (Δ) chloromethanes, (\square) bromomethanes and (\oplus) iodomethanes.

scale of electronegativity, as has been done by Thomas, while the curve in Fig. 5(b) shows the same thing using the scale due to Mande *et al.* and making use of the electronegativity value of hydrogen as obtained in the present work. A regression analysis shows that both the curves are linear but in the curve given in Fig. 5(b) the scatter for the different compounds is larger. At the first sight this result appeared to us to be somewhat disturbing. Hence, in order to see the direct effect of the ligands on the carbon atom $1s$ binding energy, we have calculated instead of the $\sum_1 (\chi_i - \chi_{\text{H}})$ values, the values of $\sum_1 (\chi_{\text{C}} - \chi_i)$, where i stands for all the ligands including hydrogen. These values are given in the last column of Table 5. In Fig. 6 are plotted the values of the carbon $1s$ binding energy

Fig. 6. Variation of the carbon $1s$ -binding energies for the halomethanes with $\sum_1 (\chi_{\text{C}} - \chi_i)$: (●) CH_4 , (O) fluoromethanes ($\Delta S_{\text{F}} = -0.90$), (Δ) chloromethanes ($\Delta S_{\text{Cl}} = -0.82$), (\square) bromomethanes ($\Delta S_{\text{Br}} = -0.63$) and (\oplus) iodomethanes ($\Delta S_{\text{I}} = -0.41$).

in different halomethanes against the values of $\sum_1 (\chi_{\text{C}} - \chi_i)$. We obtain four separate linear curves for different halomethane families which show the direct effect of the ligands on the electronic structure of the carbon atom. In the cases of fluoro- and the chloromethane families, these curves lie very close to each other, but our least-squares analysis shows them to be slightly different. The slopes (S) of these lines for the different families when plotted against the atomic numbers (Z) of the respective halogens, are shown in Fig. 7. The S versus Z curve is found to be linear and shows that the slopes of the lines S are in the sequence $S_{\text{F}} < S_{\text{Cl}} < S_{\text{Br}} < S_{\text{I}}$, which is the expected

result on the electronegativity criterion. We tried to resolve the curve in Fig. 5(a) in a similar fashion for the different halomethanes but the effort was not successful. This result too indicates that our electronegativity values including that of hydrogen are more realistic than those given by the earlier workers.

XANES and electronegativity :

It is well known⁴⁵ that the X-ray absorption discontinuities show certain features within and very close to the main absorption edges. The X-ray

TABLE 6—DATA ON CARBON K-ABSORPTION EDGE ENERGIES IN FLUOROMETHANES

Sl. no.	Compd.	E_{σ} (eV)	$\sum_1 (\chi_C - \chi_1)$
1.	CH ₃ F	298.5	2.71
2.	CH ₂ F ₂	295.0	-0.34
3.	CHF ₃	291.9	-3.39
4.	CF ₄	289.1	-6.44

Fig. 7. Variations between the slopes of the lines ΔS , in Fig. 4 and atomic number Z of the halogens.

absorption near edge structure is commonly called XANES. The different features in XANES are known to be sensitive to chemical combination⁴⁶. Sette *et al.*⁴⁷ reported the XANES features in the K -

absorption edge spectrum of carbon in a few compounds. In Table 6 are given along with $\sum_1 (\chi_C - \chi_1)$ values, the energy values of the shape resonance peak E_{σ} for the compounds CH₃F, CH₂F₂, CHF₃ and CF₄ measured by Sette *et al.* This peak is attributed by them to the transition of the $1s$ -electron into a σ^* antibonding state. In Fig. 8 are plotted the values of E_{σ} against $\sum_1 (\chi_C - \chi_1)$ which gives the charge on the central carbon atom

Fig. 8. Plot of the energy position of the σ -shape resonance versus $\sum_1 (\chi_C - \chi_1)$.

as mentioned in the section 4. We note that as the number of hydrogen atoms in the fluoromethanes decreases, the energy of the σ^* peak also decreases. Thus this curve brings out very well the effect of electronegativity, particularly that of hydrogen, on the shift of the X-ray resonance peak. It would have been interesting to compare similar experimental data for other halomethanes, but unfortunately the data are not available.

Concluding remarks :

Mande and coworkers have earlier given the electronegativity values of most of the elements between $Z = 3$ and 92. In the present work we have estimated the value of the electronegativity of hydrogen by extrapolation of the electronegativity values of the group IA elements, all of which are characterised by only one s -electron in their outermost orbital. Correlations of electronegativity values with the data on heats of formation of organic compounds, ¹³C nmr shifts, carbon $1s$ -level shifts in XPS and the main edge feature in carbon K -absorption edge spectra in halomethane families indicate that our electronegativity value of hydrogen, which is considerably lower than the value given by earlier workers, is more reasonable.

Our result can be utilised to study spectroscopic as well as physicochemical properties of many kinds of materials which involve hydrogen, such as metal hydrides, various kinds of organic compounds, polymers etc. We hope that chemists, physicists, and materials scientists would try our values of the electronegativity of hydrogen and other elements in the interpretation of various kinds of experimental results.

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